

A Flexible, Efficient and Robust Method for AI-driven Power Control in D-MIMO

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Abstract—In distributed multiple-input multiple-output (D-MIMO) networks, max-min fairness power control (MMFPC) is a commonly used strategy to optimize the spectral efficiencies of users. The optimal solution of MMFPC requires high complexity operations and hence deep neural network based artificial intelligence (AI) solutions are proposed to decrease the complexity. Although quite accurate models can be achieved by using AI under constrained assumptions, these models have a practical limitation of handling varying size inputs and outputs which results from the dynamic nature of the network. In this work, we propose a flexible and efficient solution which solves these limitations and help to enable wide adaptation of AI-driven solution in real world settings. Our proposed solution leverages the use of unsupervised learning and eliminates the need for labeled training data. We also show that unsupervised learning strategy has an additional benefit of providing robustness to potential training input perturbations. Detailed simulations reveal the effectiveness of our proposed solution.

Index Terms—Distributed MIMO, cell-free massive MIMO, power control, deep learning, robustness, 6G.

I. INTRODUCTION

In a dynamic spectrum environment influenced by channel, interference, and traffic impacts, wireless networks must carry out challenging tasks. Deep learning has become an essential asset for helping with a variety of wireless communication challenges [1]. Many wireless network problems, including power control for multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems, signal authentication, RF signal classification, spectrum sensing, and anti-jamming have been addressed using deep neural networks (DNN) [2].

Distributed MIMO (D-MIMO), also known as cell-free massive MIMO, is a promising radio access network technology where many radio units (RUs), connected to a central processor (CP) via wireless/wired fronthaul links, are distributed in a region to increase the macro diversity and mitigate path-loss and shadowing effects in wireless systems [3]. D-MIMO is expected to be one of the main antenna deployment options in 6G. By its distributed nature, D-MIMO provides more uniform performance to users compared to collocated massive MIMO currently used in 5G, where many antenna elements are installed onto a large tower. To maximize the performance and guarantee uniformly equal and good spectral efficiency (SE) to each user, the available transmit power of RUs should be allocated to the users according to the channel conditions. The power control problem in D-MIMO requires

optimization of precoding coefficients between RUs and user equipment (UE). There are different precoding algorithms proposed for D-MIMO. Although centralized zero-forcing (ZF) and minimum mean-square error (MMSE) [4] precoding algorithms theoretically perform well, under realistic conditions including synchronization errors, their advantages might be lost. On the other hand, the maximal ratio transmission (MRT) precoding algorithm can be locally implemented at RUs using the conjugates of channel coefficients between the corresponding RU and UE, which is easy to implement.

For MRT precoding, several academic papers shown that power control is crucial to obtain a good performance. Max-min fairness power control (MMFPC) is one of the most famous power control methods that satisfies uniform quality-of-service to all users jointly served within the same time/frequency resource block [5]. As D-MIMO intends to provide uniform and ubiquitous service for all users, MMFPC is quite attractive. Although there is an exact analytical solution for the MMFPC problem, the computational complexity of this solution is very high. Hence, low complexity DNN based AI solutions [6] are generally the preferred choice to approximate analytical solution.

Existing DNN-based power control solutions have been shown to perform well under constrained simulation environments where the number of RUs and UEs are fixed [7]. However, in practical scenarios, this strong assumption does not hold. Under the dynamic nature of the wireless networks where the number of UEs change in time, traditional DNN-based solutions might not be used as these models cannot handle inputs/outputs with varying sizes. Besides, existing supervised learning methodologies require optimal power control coefficients to be known during model training which make data preparation and model training even more difficult [8]. Lastly, any kind of intentional (i.e., poisoning attack scenario) or unintentional (i.e., measurement errors) modification in the input training data will ruin the performance of the final trained model in supervised learning [9]. To address the listed limitations, we propose a DNN-based power control method in D-MIMO that can effectively handle the issue of variable input/output size. Our proposed solution is based on unsupervised learning which does not rely on previously computed optimal power control coefficients. This makes model training more practical, adaptable and also robust to

any kind of input training data perturbations. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study that efficiently solves the power control problem in D-MIMO with variable number of UEs using unsupervised learning.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a D-MIMO network with M RUs and K UEs, where all terminals have a single antenna. We assume that all UEs are served by all RUs which are connected to a CP via fronthaul links. Fig. 1 shows an example D-MIMO network.

Fig. 1: A typical D-MIMO network with 7 RUs and 4 UEs.

In this case, the received signal at the k -th UE can be written as

$$y_k = \sum_{\ell=1}^K \sum_{m=1}^M h_{m,k} w_{m,\ell} s_{\ell} + z_k, \quad (1)$$

where y_k is the received signal of the k -th UE, $h_{m,k}$ is the channel coefficient between the m -th RU and the k -th UE, $w_{m,k}$ is the precoding coefficient of m -th RU designed for k -th UE, s_k is the intended symbol for the k -th UE satisfying $\mathbb{E}[|s_k|^2] = 1$, $\forall k$, and $z_k \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_k^2)$ is the receiver noise sample of the k -th UE. Here for simplicity, we assume that channel coefficients are perfectly known by CP. On the other hand, all findings of this study can be directly generalized to imperfect channel knowledge case. For MRT precoding, we choose precoders as

$$w_{m,k} = \sqrt{P_t \eta_{m,k}} h_{m,k}^*, \quad \forall m, k, \quad (2)$$

where P_t is the maximum transmission power for each RU, and $\eta_{m,k}$ is the power control coefficient between the m -th RU and the k -th UE. For each RU, we have a per-RU transmit power constraint which can be written as

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\left| \sum_{k=1}^K w_{m,k} s_k \right|^2 \right] = P_t \sum_{k=1}^K \eta_{m,k} \beta_{m,k} \leq P_t, \quad \forall m. \quad (3)$$

Here $\beta_{m,k} = \mathbb{E}[|h_{m,k}|^2]$ denotes the large-scale fading coefficient of the channel between m -th RU and k -th UE. By means of channel hardening obtained when the number of RUs is large, the users can extract their intended symbols only using statistical channel knowledge [10]. In this case, the desired signal of the k -th UE becomes

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \mathbb{E}[h_{m,k} w_{m,k}] s_k = \sum_{m=1}^M \sqrt{P_t \eta_{m,k}} \beta_{m,k} s_k. \quad (4)$$

Considering the desired signal part, and following the bounding approach that treats mismatch and interference terms as Gaussian noise [10], we can write UE signal-to-interference-and-noise-ratios (SINRs) as

$$\text{SINR}_k = \frac{P_t \left(\sum_{m=1}^M \sqrt{\eta_{m,k}} \beta_{m,k} \right)^2}{P_t \sum_{\ell=1}^K \sum_{m=1}^M \eta_{m,\ell} \beta_{m,\ell} \beta_{m,k} + \sigma_k^2}. \quad (5)$$

The user SEs are found as¹

$$\text{SE}_k = \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_k). \quad (6)$$

The large-scale fading coefficients $\beta_{m,k}$'s are estimated at RU side using uplink pilot signals (sounding reference signals, SRSs). To obtain a high performance, the power control coefficients should be optimized. MMFPC optimizes the minimum SINR (or SE) in the system under power transmit constraints, i.e.,

$$(P1) \max_{\eta_{m,k}} \min_k \text{SE}_k \quad \text{such that} \quad \sum_{k=1}^K \eta_{m,k} \beta_{m,k} \leq 1. \quad (7)$$

The MMFPC problem can be optimally solved using bisection search where iterative second order cone problems are solved. It can be proved that at the optimal point, all UEs will have equal SINRs.

In Fig. 2, we observe the block scheme of analytical solution where the analytical function f solves (P1) using the large-scale fading coefficients $\beta = [\beta_{1,1}, \beta_{1,2}, \dots, \beta_{M,K}]^T$ to find the power control coefficients $\eta_{m,k}$'s. The analytical function q uses (5) and (6) to evaluate SE of UEs via β and $\eta = [\eta_{1,1} \beta_{1,1}, \eta_{1,2} \beta_{1,2}, \dots, \eta_{M,K} \beta_{M,K}]^T$ where η includes normalized power coefficients whose sum over all UEs is in between 0 and 1 for all RUs.

$$\beta \xrightarrow{f(\beta)} \eta \quad \beta, \eta \xrightarrow{q(\beta, \eta)} \text{SE}$$

Fig. 2: Analytical solution. It is denoted by f and it finds η by analytically solving the problem (P1). Here q denotes the analytical function used to find the SE of UEs from β and η .

A. Existing AI-Based Methodology

Although MMFPC problem can be analytically solved, the solution requires complex steps and hence usage of AI models becomes advantageous. In the literature, it was shown that [11] the complexity of the analytical solution of MMFPC is $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{K} + MM^3 K^4)$. As we see from the complexity formula, analytical solution is very complex and hence some AI methods were proposed to decrease the complexity without sacrificing the performance. In [7], a model for solving such a power control problem is given. We can consider the input of the model as the augmented channel vector β . We prefer to define the input in dB scale by considering $10 \log_{10}(\beta)$. The

¹In practice, we should also put a constant reduction factor to take the pilot overhead into account.

output of the AI function can be considered as the normalized power vector η_{AI} which is defined as η .

The vector β includes all channel knowledge and hence the power control problem can be solved in CP that each RU is connected to. This connection is provided by fronthaul links in D-MIMO. Hence, RUs first send their $\beta_{m,k}$ values to CP and AI model is operated in the CP to determine optimal power control coefficients. The results are sent back to RUs over fronthaul links to transmit the signals with related power values.

In Fig. 3, we observe a typical AI operation for power control task. The related AI model estimates power control coefficients η_{AI} leading to SEs SE_{AI} for UEs.

Fig. 3: AI-based solution. The AI solution is denoted by \tilde{f} and it approximates f by maintaining $SE \approx SE_{AI}$. Here SE_{AI} is the vector of SEs obtained by the AI model.

To solve the MMFPC problem, DNNs are widely used. These models can efficiently solve MMFPC for a fixed number of RUs and UEs. For a fixed M and K , the input and output size of the DNN becomes MK . On the other hand, in practice, the number of UEs connected to the live network is not fixed and dynamically changes in a short period of time. Despite this, to the best of our knowledge, no earlier research has offered a solution to the problem of variable input/output size. Most of the prior works consider a simple scenario where the number of RUs and UEs in the network are fixed so that a traditional DNN architecture will work with fixed size input/output. However, the dynamic nature of the live networks makes standard DNN-based approaches useless. There are two main existing approaches proposed in the literature [8], [12]:

Method 1: For each K value, a separate model is trained as in Fig. 4. In this approach, one can select the related model according to the number of UEs.

Fig. 4: Approach-1 with many separate DNNs.

Method 2: The idea of zero-padding can be applied to train a single large model. For the maximum possible K value, which is K_{max} , we train a large model and use this model with zero-padding input to solve the problem for all

$K \leq K_{max}$ values as in Fig. 5. The idea of padding the inputs of different DNN architectures has been studied in [12] where the authors experimentally showed the effects of different padding strategies on model performance. In [8], the authors work on DNN-based power control problem in cell-free massive MIMO, considering a maximum value for M and K and constructing the architecture based on this maximum value. When a smaller number of M or K is encountered, they apply zero padding to their input.

Fig. 5: Approach-2 with a large DNN and zero-padded input.

B. Problems with the Existing Methodology

There are some problems for both methods.

Problems with Method 1: When the possible number of UEs is large, we need many separate models. This will increase the training time and complicates the maintenance of the models. Furthermore, as the number of UEs connected to the network is rapidly changing, this approach requires frequent model switching which may be impractical. In 5G NR, up to 16 UEs can be jointly served in multi-user MIMO [13] meaning that this approach requires 16 different DNNs.

The static nature of conventional DNN implementations can be better understood as follows: In the conventional approach, assuming that we have M RUs and K UEs, the channel input β and power control output η of the AI model is a 1-d vector of size MK . Therefore, the dimensions of the first and the last hidden layers are adjusted as $\mathbb{R}^{A \times MK}$ and $\mathbb{R}^{MK \times B}$ where the first hidden layer has A neurons and the last hidden layer has B neurons as in Fig. 6. This induces a binding requirement to the number of RUs and UEs in the network. Even we have a chance to fix the number of RUs in the network, we still cannot have the possibility to fix the number of UEs in the network. This means that we will need a large number of different network architectures which need to be trained and deployed to cover all the possibilities. Obviously, this kind of approach is not practical at all.

Problems with Method 2: This method has two main disadvantages. Firstly, regardless of the actual number of UEs, we always run a large model designed for the maximum possible K value, and hence the complexity is higher than it should be. The DNN model processes inputs and outputs of dimension MK_{max} which is larger than MK creating some extra computation load. Secondly, this method requires an input size MK_{max} and inserting zeros (we need to insert $M(K_{max} - K)$ zeros) to the input to make its size equal

Fig. 6: As-Is DNN implementation.

to MK_{\max} might decrease the training accuracy leading to a degradation in performance.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

To effectively handle the issue of variable input/output size for DNN implementation, we propose to preprocess the channel input vector. Instead of using 1-d input vector, we suggest reshaping the input vector to 2-d matrix with dimensions denoted as $\mathbb{R}^{M \times K}$. We then adjust the number of neurons in the network layers in such a way to keep the output of all layers of network as 2-d, by keeping the second dimension K always, which is the number of UEs. This way, the effect of variable number of UEs in the network is eliminated. We will only need to consider the size of the RUs in the network which might be fixed as M , and the variability of the number of UEs will be handled with the 2-d flow of data through the network layers as in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: Proposed operation with 2-d input/output.

Once we get the output from the last layer, we then reshape the output vector from 2-d ($\mathbb{R}^{M \times K}$) to 1-d (\mathbb{R}^{MK}) again. This kind of implementation will work when M is fixed, and K changes.

The performance of the proposed solution which depends solely on dense layers might be somehow limited, especially for scenarios where the number of UEs get higher. This is because the columns of the hidden layer outputs will depend on the channel statistics of corresponding UEs which are

based on each individual RU. And the effect of the interaction of the UEs will be taken care of by the objective loss function which is defined as maximizing minimum SE value which is calculated by (5) and (6).

To increase the performance of the overall solution, we suggest to incorporate the use of convolutional layers which are followed by dense (linear) layers. The convolution operation moves a $c \times c$ dimensional kernel matrix \mathbf{C} over 2-d the input. Kernels combine channel information of different UEs from a small, local area of 2-d channel information input matrix. Also the kernel is applied globally across the whole 2-d input to produce a matrix of outputs, hence we will have a chance to cover all parts of the data. With backpropagation coming from the objective loss function, the kernels will have the task of learning weights to produce the input features. Additionally, because the kernel itself is applied across the entire 2-d input data, the features the kernel learn are expected to be general enough to come from any part of the original 2-d channel information input matrix. The important thing to note here is the size of the kernels together with the padding and stride values. One should choose the padding and stride values in such a way to keep the first two dimensions M and K fixed through the flow of data within the network. One alternative can be to apply 3×3 kernel for 2-d convolution (conv2d) layers with padding and stride equal to 1 to keep the first two dimensions fixed as M and K as in Fig. 8. Other alternative can be to apply 5×5 kernel for conv2d layers with padding 2 and stride 1. The reason to apply 1×1 convolution is to shrink the number of channels down to 1 to keep the dimension $M \times K$ before feeding to dense layers.

Fig. 8: Proposed operation with convolution layers.

To satisfy the per-RU transmit power constraint in (7) for each RU m , we suggest using sigmoid activation function at the DNN output layer and apply a normalization operation to output $\eta_{m,k}$ values to guarantee that the constraints are satisfied. In the normalization operation, for each m , we evaluate the sum $\sum_{k=1}^K \eta_{m,k} \beta_{m,k}$ and if the result exceeds 1, we suggest multiplying each $\eta_{m,k}$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ with a constant c_m so that $\sum_{k=1}^K c_m \eta_{m,k} \beta_{m,k} = 1$. The flowchart of this part is given in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9: DNN output layer steps.

The summary of our proposed solution is depicted in Fig. 10. We suggest converting the dimensions of channel information input vector from 1-d to 2-d. After this preprocessing information, we align the weights of the network in such a way to maintain the 2-d flow of data (by obeying our proposed implementation details) and assure that the output vector is again a 2-d vector with size M and K as described above. After that, we convert the 2-d output vector to 1-d vector again.

Fig. 10: Summarized steps of the proposed algorithm.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

To show the effectiveness of our method, we perform various numerical simulations. We uniformly distribute all RUs and UEs in a 500 m x 500 m square region. Other simulation parameters are given in Table I.

TABLE I: Simulation parameters

Parameter	Model and/or Value
Carrier frequency, bandwidth	1.9 GHz, 20 MHz
Path-loss	$[PL_{m,k}]_{dB}$ is chosen according to the 3-slope model in [5]
Shadowing	$[\beta_{m,k,sh}]_{dB} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 8^2)$
Channel model	$h_{m,k} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \beta_{m,k})$ where $[\beta_{m,k}]_{dB} = [PL_{m,k}]_{dB} + [\beta_{m,k,sh}]_{dB}$
Average RU transmit power, UE receiver noise power	$P_t = 0.2$ W, $\sigma_k^2 = -92$ dBm, $\forall k$

We have trained a model based on our proposed method in a similar manner shown in Fig. 8. We have used 200K train data for each K value to train our unsupervised model, and used 20K test data for each K as well to test the performance of our model. We trained the model for 75 epochs with an initial learning rate (LR) of 0.001 using Adam optimizer and decreased the LR to half after each 20 epoch. Our model is built based on 5 successive residual blocks (each consisting of 2 convolutional layers) followed by channel averaging and 2 dense layers. Instead of using a previously labeled training data and applying supervised training on the input-output pairs, we have performed unsupervised training where our aim is to maximize the minimum user rate in the network. The input to our model is channel vector β and the output is the normalized power control vector η_{AI} . Training dataset is composed of scenarios with fix number of RUs ($M = 16$) and varying size of UEs in the network ranging from 1 to 8. In the evaluation phase, we test the performance of our model in different scenarios and show that our single model can effectively handle the variable input/output size problem.

A. Comparison of AI and analytical solutions

Firstly, we compare the SE results of the proposed AI method and the analytical solution. We generate the AI model using unsupervised learning approach by feeding inputs β for $M = 16$ and $K = 1, 2, \dots, 8$. The model aims to maximize the minimum SE of all UEs in the unsupervised learning stage. Fig. 11 shows the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of per-user SEs for analytical and AI solutions.

Fig. 11: The comparison of the proposed AI model and the analytical solution.

We observe in Fig. 11 that SE values obtained by the AI method is very close to those of the analytical solution. In Table II, which is derived from the results given in Fig. 11, we see the numerical comparison of AI and analytical SEs in 5th percentile² and median (50th percentile). We again observe that the results of the AI is very close to those of analytical solution showing that the proposed approach approximates the optimal analytical solution very well. Furthermore, notice that although the model is generated using (M, K) pairs only for $1 \leq K \leq 8$, we can obtain very accurate results also for $K = 9$. This proves that the proposed method has a capability to cover larger K values which are not considered at the time of model training and shows the generalization capability of our proposed solution.

B. Robustness of the proposed method

Secondly, we observe the effects of perturbations on the input channel vector β used in the training stage. We assume that a random Gaussian perturbation with 0 dB mean and 8 dB standard deviation (which is equal to the shadowing standard deviation) is added to each element of the input channel vector β in the training stage. This perturbation can be observed due to a poisoning attack on the system [9] or it can be due to measurement errors for the channel estimation. Fig. 12 shows the CDF of resulting SE values.

As observed in Fig. 12 and also in Table II, the SE values obtained under training input data perturbations are

²5th percentile SE shows SE values at which CDF is equal to 0.05.

TABLE II: SEs in bps/Hz for proposed AI (with and without training perturbations) and the analytical solution.

Parameters	K	AI SE (without perturb.)		AI SE (with perturb.)		Analytical SE		AI-Analytical Gap (%)		Effect of Perturb. (%)	
		5th percentile	Median	5th percentile	Median	5th percentile	Median	5th percentile	Median	5th percentile	Median
16	1	3.26	3.59	3.26	3.59	3.26	3.59	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
16	2	2.63	2.84	2.62	2.84	2.66	2.85	1.14	0.35	0.38	0.00
16	3	2.26	2.42	2.25	2.41	2.29	2.44	1.33	0.83	0.44	0.41
16	4	1.99	2.12	1.98	2.11	2.03	2.14	2.01	0.94	0.50	0.47
16	5	1.77	1.90	1.76	1.89	1.80	1.91	1.69	0.53	0.56	0.53
16	6	1.61	1.72	1.60	1.71	1.66	1.74	3.11	1.16	0.62	0.58
16	7	1.46	1.57	1.45	1.56	1.51	1.60	3.42	1.91	0.68	0.64
16	8	1.35	1.46	1.34	1.45	1.42	1.49	5.19	2.05	0.74	0.68
16	9	1.23	1.35	1.22	1.34	1.33	1.38	8.13	2.22	0.81	0.74

Fig. 12: The effect of training input perturbations on the performance.

very close to those values obtained in Fig. 11 where there is no perturbation. These results show that our regression model is robust to such kind of input variations in the training stage which is expected thanks to the unsupervised learning approach used. Because the aim of the regression task is to learn the underlying nonlinear function which maps the input-output pairs. Also, applying any kind of intentional or unintentional perturbation to the input vector will not change the model learning behavior in the unsupervised learning approach, as the model will still be trying to find the best output based on the given input data.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we proposed a method which helps to find a solution to a real life DNN implementation problem for a wireless task which is caused by the dynamically changing nature of the network. We provide a practical solution which can increase wide adaptation of DNNs in D-MIMO use case without sacrificing time and computational complexity. Our solution eliminates the need for training/deploying high number of separate DNN architectures and also eliminates the use of sparse and huge architectures. We may also benefit from a sustainability standpoint by reducing the amount of energy consumed by the network using our solution. Besides, we showed that employing an unsupervised learning strategy will have additional benefits of reducing the impact of possible poisoning attacks or measurement errors to the AI model training for these kind of regression tasks.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) through the 1515 Frontier Research and Development Laboratories Support Program under Project 5169902, and has been partly funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under Grant Agreement No: 101096034 (VERGE Project).

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